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GHANA**

**Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices of Diabetics on Diabetes Mellitus: A Cross-Sectional
Study among Diabetic Patients at the Enyiresi Government Hospital in the Atiwa East
District of Ghana**

By

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated first and foremost to the Almighty God for His abundant Grace, Favour, and Mercies for the successful completion of this work. Secondly, to my supportive husband, Mr. Ishmael Laryea Tetteh, for his enormous support and encouragement. Lastly, to Mr. Joseph Gyimah for taking time out of his busy schedule to analyze my work for me. I am eternally grateful. God bless you all.

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a term used to refer to a set of metabolic diseases defined by hyperglycaemia index (DM). Errors in the metabolism of proteins, carbohydrates, and fats cause chronic issues such as microvascular, macrovascular, and neuropathic disorders. The study assessed the level of knowledge regarding diabetes and how it influences diabetics' attitudes and behaviors, which have an impact on how they manage their glycaemic status. A descriptive cross-sectional design was conducted involving 150 diabetic patients at the Enyiresi Government Hospital in the Atiwa East District of Ghana. A questionnaire was used to gather information on sociodemographic characteristics, some anthropometric indicators (weight, height, BMI), knowledge, attitude, and practices on diabetes. Data were analyzed using SPSS (version 21.0). Statistical significance for all testing was set as 0.05. Of the total 150 participants, 55.4% were overweight/obese. The mean BMI was 27.07 ± 5.47 . About 50.7% of the diabetic patients had good knowledge, attitudes, and practices on diabetes. Diabetes patients' knowledge, attitude, and practices were significantly associated with their nutritional status ($p=0.0002$). Patients' education level was significantly associated with knowledge scores ($p=0.0001$). Patients who had a high level of education also had good knowledge of diabetes. Again, diabetic patients' marital status ($p=0.0003$), average income ($p=0.0002$), gender ($p=0.0001$), and age ($p=0.0002$) were statistically significant with their knowledge, attitude, and practice scores. Female patients had more knowledge than male patients. Furthermore, diabetic patient's knowledge was significantly associated with a relative with first-degree diabetes ($p=0.0004$). Patients who had relatives with first-degree diabetes were knowledgeable of diabetes. The study concludes that the level of knowledge regarding diabetes was found to be high and with a positive significant influence on attitude. Lifestyle activities should be integral in the management and control of diabetes.

Key words: Diabetes mellitus, glycaemia, KAP, BMI

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADA – American Diabetes Association
BMI – Body Mass Index
CHO – Carbohydrate
CVD – cardiovascular disease
DF – Dietary Fibre
DM – Diabetes Mellitus
FBG – Fasting Blood Glucose
FPG – Fasting Plasma Glucose
GAD65 – Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase 65
GDM – Gestational Diabetes Mellitus
GI – Glycaemic Index
GL – Glycaemic Load
GLUT4 – Glucose Transporter 4
GR – Glycaemic Response
HbA1C - Glycated haemoglobin A1c
hPL – Human Placental Lactogen
IDF – International Diabetes Federation
IFG – Impaired Fasting Glucose
IGT – Impaired Glucose Tolerance
IR – Insulin Resistance
KAP – Knowledge Attitude and Practices
LADA - Latent Autoimmune Diabetes in adults
LADPSG - International Association of the Diabetes and Pregnancy Study Groups
LCHF – Low Carbohydrate High Fat
MA – Microalbuminuria
MMOL – Millimole
NCD – Non- Communicable Diseases
PPG – Post - Prandial Glucose
SPSS - Statistical Package for Social Services
T1DM – Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus
T2DM – Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus
TECOS - Trial Evaluating Cardiovascular Outcomes with Sitagliptin
UNO – United Nations Organization
WHO – World Health Organization
WHR – Waist to Hip Ratio

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Diabetes mellitus (DM), commonly known as diabetes, is a global health challenge marked by raised glucose levels in the blood brought on by abnormalities in the generation, action, or both of insulin (Ismaeil *et al.*, 2013). This metabolic disorder affects millions worldwide and is associated with chronic complications such as microvascular, macrovascular, and neuropathic disorders.

On a global scale, the rise in diabetes is alarming and by 2030, diabetes is estimated to affect 366 million people and become the seventh leading cause of death (WHO, 2016). This surge in diabetes is driven by factors like inappropriate eating, physical inactivity, smoking, excessive alcohol intake, and inadequate sleep (Kumar *et al.*, 2013). In 2016, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported a global incidence of 8.5%, with 422 million adult diabetics worldwide (Zimmet *et al.*, 2016). Shockingly, projections indicate that by 2045, there will be a staggering 700 million individuals living with diabetes (10.9%) globally. While diabetes was previously thought to be uncommon in Africa, now, it is a chronic illness in Sub-Saharan Africa. Countries like Ghana have witnessed a substantial increase in diabetes cases, driven partly by lifestyle changes (Kumar *et al.*, 2013). The International Diabetes Federation estimates that 15.5 million adults in Africa aged 20 to 79 have diabetes, with a high prevalence rate of 69.2% and many remain undiagnosed (Bekele, 2018). The rate of Africans with this disease is expected to shoot up to over 41 million by 2045, imposing substantial financial and health costs (International Diabetes Federation, 2017).

In Ghana, the diabetes epidemic is a pressing concern. In 2017, it was estimated that 518,400 Ghanaians had diabetes, with a prevalence rate of 5% and a rising daily incidence (International Diabetes Federation, 2017). Diabetes-related mortality in Ghana was also a significant concern,

with heart attacks, blindness, and lower limb amputations among the consequences (Facts & Diabetes, 2011). Patterns of diabetes prevalence in Ghana mirrored those in other sub-Saharan African countries, with rates ranging from 6.2% to 13.9%, a stark contrast to earlier studies that reported less than 0.02% prevalence (Kantanka *et al.*, 2014).

Understanding diabetes is crucial for early detection and effective management. Informed individuals are more likely to seek medical attention promptly and engage in healthier behaviors (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2017). Knowledge about diabetes empowers individuals to make informed decisions regarding their diet, medication, physical activity, and overall lifestyle. This knowledge is especially vital for recognizing and addressing hypo- or hyperglycaemia. Attitudes toward diabetes play a significant role in self-management and positive attitudes, such as empowerment and self-efficacy, can motivate individuals to adhere to treatment plans and engage in healthy behaviors. Conversely, stigma, misconceptions, and negative attitudes can hinder diabetes management and lead to psychological distress.

Effective self-care practices encompass various aspects of diabetes management, including diet, medication adherence, physical activity, blood glucose monitoring, and healthcare utilization. Educating individuals with diabetes has been shown to improve clinical outcomes and quality of life (Serrano-Gil *et al.*, 2010). However, despite advancements in research, patient understanding of the condition remains limited, impacting its management (Fatema *et al.*, 2017; Mohammadi, 2015).

Uncontrolled glycaemic status in diabetes is linked to chronic hyperglycaemia and long-term complications. Maintaining glycated haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels below 7% is recommended for long-term glycaemic control (Alakhali & Mohammad, 2014). Suboptimal glycaemic control is associated with complications such as diabetic ketoacidosis, micro and macrovascular problems, and poor outcomes (Kibirige *et al.*, 2017).

Patient education is a critical component of diabetes management as it relies on the patient's ability to practice self-care in their daily lives (Al-Maskari *et al.*, 2013). Knowledge about diabetes risk and the importance of seeking appropriate care and treatment can help patients maintain control over their condition (Ayele *et al.*, 2012).

Diabetes mellitus is, thus, a global health crisis that has reached alarming proportions. From a global perspective to the African context and specifically in Ghana, the prevalence of diabetes is on the rise, with significant health and economic implications. Effective management of diabetes requires a combination of patient education, positive attitudes, and proactive self-care practices to achieve glycaemic control and prevent complications. Addressing this growing epidemic is essential to improving the quality of life for individuals with diabetes and reducing its burden on healthcare systems and economies worldwide.

1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Globally, regionally, and locally, diabetes prevalence and related complications pose significant public health challenges. The International Diabetes Federation (2017) predicted that 518,400 Ghanaians were living with diabetes, and the prevalence of this condition was increasing at a concerning rate of 5%. This escalating trend is evident in the records of the Enyiresi Government Hospital, which reported a substantial rise in the figures of diabetes patients, with 965 cases in 2020 and 1023 in 2021. These occurrences were widespread, highlighting the chronic nature of diabetes and the pressing concern it poses.

Recent years have seen diabetes emerge as a leading cause of mortality worldwide, including in Ghana. In Ghana, the impact of diabetes was starkly evident, with 9,778 deaths among adults aged 20 to 79 (International Diabetes Federation, 2017). This predominantly affects the adult working population, a cornerstone of national progress. Thus, the consequences of diabetes, such as reduced productivity and potential underdevelopment, loom large. Moreover, social

disparities may intensify if complications like blindness, stroke, amputation, and job loss are not effectively addressed.

Effective diabetes management hinges on the support healthcare providers offer to patients in their self-care efforts. Regrettably, research has unveiled inconsistencies in this support system, with diabetic care providers failing to consistently assist patients with self-management and not consistently tailoring care to meet individual needs (Mwangome, *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, diabetes healthcare historically centered on biomedical aspects, often prioritizing medication over psychological factors such as knowledge, attitude, and practice. Nevertheless, empirical studies have underscored the intricate connection between these psychological factors and diabetic self-care practices, highlighting their significant influence (Ahmed *et al.*, 2015; Services, 2014).

Given these findings, it is imperative to ensure that both patients and healthcare professionals are well-informed about beneficial methods such as diabetes care education, which encompasses self-care practices. The World Health Organization has identified several risk factors associated with diabetes mellitus, including unhealthy eating habits, lack of exercise, smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, and poor sleep patterns (Hu, 2011). Knowledgeable diabetics are more likely to achieve better long-term glucose control, underscoring the significance of information, optimism, and adherence to best practices in diabetes management (Al-Maskari *et al.*, 2013).

Patients play a crucial role in managing their diabetes by understanding the associated risks and seeking appropriate care. Unfortunately, many diabetes patients, particularly in regions with a high prevalence of the condition, often lack sufficient knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAPs) related to diabetes (Ajzen *et al.*, 2011). This widespread lack of access to information highlights the need for tailored diabetes care treatments that consider the KAP of patients. Consequently, the purpose of the current research was aimed at reviewing the

understanding, attitudes, and practices among diagnosed diabetic patients regarding diabetes mellitus, with the goal of bridging the information gap and improving diabetes care.

1.3. JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

Examining the understanding (knowledge), beliefs (attitudes), and behaviors (practices) surrounding diabetes, this study can offer valuable insights for crafting tailored prevention and treatment strategies for patients. Such findings can serve to identify specific diabetes-related actions and knowledge gaps among individuals living with the condition.

1.4. GENERAL OBJECTIVE

The main focus of the current work was to review the understanding, mindsets and practices on the disease among diabetic patients at Enyiresi Government Hospital in the Atiwa East District of Ghana.

1.5. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To estimate the level of understanding, attitudes as well as practices on diabetes among diabetic patients.
2. To determine the nutritional status among the diabetes patients using their BMI.
3. To investigate the correlation linking BMI status and socio-demographic characteristics of patients and their level of knowledge, attitude, and practice.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. CONCEPT OF DIABETES MELLITUS

Contrary to acute illnesses, where patients are typically treated without their active involvement, diabetes care is difficult and primarily self-management is required (Chlebowy *et al.*, 2010). To achieve and maintain adequate glycaemic control and prevent further complications, diabetic individuals and/or their families must take an active role in treating their illness. To maintain effective glycaemic control, it is crucial for the individual to pay close attention to diet, engage in regular physical activities, monitor blood sugar levels, take medications as prescribed, and take care of their feet (Chlebowy *et al.*, 2010). It is imperative that individuals with diabetes have access to information and tools to improve their individual participation in diabetes self-care (Daly *et al.*, 2009). Le Roux and colleagues assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of 255 diabetes of type 2 patients getting care at public healthcare institutions in the Free State, South Africa, to achieve this goal (Le Roux *et al.*, 2019).

Diabetes mellitus is a term used to refer to a set of metabolic diseases defined by hyperglycaemia index (DM). The most common condition recognized worldwide in the healthcare industry is diabetes. This is clear from the rise in diabetes disease reporting, which is anticipated to reach 366 million people by 2030 and rank as the seventh highest cause of death (Kapoor, 2013; WHO, 2016). Problems in the metabolism of proteins, carbohydrates, and fats cause chronic issues such microvascular, macrovascular, and neuropathic disorders (Ismaeil *et al.*, 2013). It is a hyperglycaemia syndrome brought on by a total or partial lack of insulin in the blood or by diminished insulin efficacy (Kumar *et al.*, 2013). Globally, diabetes mellitus is estimated by the WHO to be a factor associated with early death, cardiovascular and kidney illnesses linked to poor eating, inactivity or insufficient exercise, smoking, excessive

alcohol intake, and inappropriate sleeping habits (Kumar *et al.*, 2013). The disease, often associated with aging and older individuals, is gradually spreading to young adults and adolescents, according to Arnett *et al.* (2019), Aranda (2019), and Morgan *et al.* (2021). Obesity, improper eating practices and absence of activity is the primary attributes to the issue, according to Aranda (2019) and Arnett *et al.* (2019).

In Ghana, diabetes of type 2 has a lengthy record but until the latter half of the 20th century, very little was known about the illness. Amoah *et al.* (2012) discovered a widely held belief that diabetes is a disease of the wealthy in their extensive research of the condition across the country. On the other hand, the United Nations Organization (UNO adoption) of the Millennium Development Goals (2000-2015) and the Sustainable Development Goals (2015-2030) has revived awareness of the threat posed by type 2 diabetes in Ghana at the national, regional, and district levels (Aikins *et al.*, 2019). There is a wealth of recent knowledge in the literature about diabetes in the Ashanti region of Ghana, becoming the country's highest level of type 2 diabetes scientific writing (Sarfo-Kantanka *et al.*, 2014). For instance, Addo *et al.*, (2017) discovered that in Metropolitan Kumasi, the prevalence of diabetes rises with higher levels of schooling. Agbogli *et al.* (2017) discovered that sedentary living habits, being overweight, and obesity were the main risk factors for diabetes in the Oforikrom Municipality. Aikins *et al.* (2019) also identified psychosocial risk factors (lifestyle and behavioral) as the primary cause of diabetes mellitus type 2 in humans in the vicinity. The risk factors include physical inactivity, poor dietary habits, excessive alcohol consumption, eating poorly, smoking, and eating late at night (Aikins *et al.*, 2019). However, there is no study that synthesized all primary research on type 2 diabetes mellitus to determine the most common risk factors of the disease existing in the study region. One should not undervalue the importance of knowledge synthesis in any given field. Wohlin (2014) asserts that systematic reviews aid in the identification, assessment, and synthesis of the findings of all pertinent

individual research on a health-related topic, making the available information more understandable to decision-makers (Wohlin *et al.*, 2014).

2.2. PREVALENCE AND GLOBAL BURDEN OF DIABETES MELLITUS

In the twenty-first century, diabetes continues to rank among the most common illnesses that warrant public health attention. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) (2020) reckons that 463 million individuals worldwide, or one out of eleven people, have the illness. In a similar vein, the World Health Organization reports that diabetes has claimed over 4.2 million lives worldwide. Atop US\$ 760 billion has been allocated to the fight against diabetes worldwide for the year 2019 (IDF, 2020). Despite this effort, the WHO (2021) reported that more than 374 million additional people are already at a high risk of acquiring diabetes-related problems. Similarly, the IDF (2020) forecast that over 700 million individuals worldwide are predicted to be afflicted by the disease by the end of 2045 as a result of shifting psychosocial and institutional elements. Because of these recent breakthroughs, diabetes is now considered to be among the top four noncommunicable diseases (International Diabetes Federation, 2020). Type 2 diabetes mellitus, the most prevalent form of the disease, currently represents over 90% of all victims of diabetes globally (Mbaye, 2014; Zimmet, 2017; International Diabetes Federation, 2019).

According to the WHO (2016) estimates, there were 422 million adult diabetics worldwide (Zimmet, *et al.*, 2016) and by the year 2030, there will be 578 million diabetics (10.2%), and by 2045, there will be 700 million (10.9%). This number, which is 4% in low-income countries, is increasing and is a threat to global public health (Saeedi, *et al.*, 2019).

Globally, diabetes mellitus (DM) and its consequences pose serious problems for public health. The prevalence of DM is rising on a global scale. According to Lin *et al.* (2020) and IDF (2019), there were approximately 463 million people living with DM worldwide in 2019

compared to 211 million in 1990, a of 120% rise. The majority (79%) of these people live in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where healthcare resources are limited and the standard of care is subpar (IDF, 2019; Flood *et al.*, 2021). Between 2012 and 2015, the number of people with diabetes diagnosed grew by 700,000 each year. The prevalence of the disease is expected to rise over time as the population ages and grows larger (Boyle, 2010; Centers for Disease Control, 2017). Globally, the prevalence of diabetes has increased significantly, hitting nearly 422 million people over the age of 18, with a 1.5 million on a yearly death rate projected. By 2030, diabetes is projected to affect above 600 million people worldwide and will rank as the 7th recognized root of death. (Rowley *et al.*, 2017).

Diabetes costs society \$245 billion in the US, including increased medical expenses, lost productivity, early mortality, and lowered quality of life due to diagnosis. (American Diabetes Association, 2012).

Despite being a global occurrence, Thomas *et al.* (2019) stated that the health disorder is gradually spreading to emerging nations, particularly those in Africa and Asia. The IDF estimates that 120 million people in China have type 2 diabetes, making the country with the highest prevalence worldwide (IDF, 2020).

Africa has experienced similar levels of type 2 diabetes cases as the rest of the world (Mbaye, 2014). According to the IDF (2015), there are currently an estimated 19.4 million adults in the region who are living with the condition, and that aggregate is slated to rise to 45 million before the end of 2045, with a prevalence rate of 3.9%. In a similar vein, the WHO estimated that over 45 million African adults aged 20 to 79 have a borderline diabetes, placing them at a high peril of developing adult-onset diabetes in some time to come. If the necessary interventions are put off, the tally is predicted to get bigger to 110 million no later than 2045 (World Health Organization, 2021).

According to a systematic review by Sarfo Kantanka *et al.* (2014), trends in the prevalence of diabetes mellitus are like those seen in other sub-Saharan African countries, with recent numbers ranging from 6.2% to 13.9%, up from the paltry prevalence rate of less than 0.02 percent of the adult population in earlier studies (Sarfo Kantanka *et al.*, 2014). These may not be alarming given that a sizable minority of persons lack a diagnosis (Aikins, *et al.*, 2013).

Due to early lifestyle change, the incidence and prevalence rate of diabetes mellitus is higher in emerging nations than in industrialized countries, particularly (Kumar *et al.*, 2013). The International Diabetes Federation estimates that 15.5 million adults in the African continent between the ages of 20 and 70 have diabetes mellitus. This region has a high prevalence (69.2%), with 55.3% of adults living in metropolitan areas having modified their lifestyles and 69.2% of adults uninformed of their medical state (Bekele, 2018).

Different continents, as well as within continents, have different risk factors that contribute to the prevalence of diabetes (NCD Risk Factor Collaboration, 2016). Specific interventions can be focused to lessen the severity and burden of the disease by comprehending and examining the prevalence of and peculiar risk factors for diabetes in sub-Saharan Africa. Some 4.5 million adults in South Africa have diabetes as of 2019, which places a significant strain on the country (IDF, 2019). A rise in obesity, poor lifestyle choices, an aging population, and urbanization are the main causes of the rising prevalence of DM in South Africa (International Diabetes Federation, 2019).

Additionally, DM is currently one of the top 10 killers in South Africa, with over 50% of deaths occurring in people of working age (International Diabetes Federation, 2019). With rates ranging from 69.3% (Tumbo *et al.*, 2013) to as high as 84% (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2016), diabetes in South Africa is exacerbated by poorly controlled glycaemic status, leading to increased healthcare costs and complications for patients. Supporting lifestyle changes and patients' participation in self-management behaviors is one of the most important measures toward lowering the burden of DM and improving health outcomes (Tumbo *et al.*, 2013; Adeniyi *et al.*, 2016). However, Ryan (2009) argued that patient education and awareness promote healthy behavior. Knowledgeable people with diabetes can more effectively manage their illness on their own, recognize possible risk factors with ease, and seek care as soon as necessary (Shrestha *et al.*, 2015). This in turn results in improved glycaemic control, a decline in complications and hospitalizations, and an overall improvement in quality of life (Phillips *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, it is critical to frequently evaluate patients' knowledge and to use that information to develop pertinent interventions that close knowledge gaps (Shrestha *et al.*, 2015; Phillips *et al.*, 2018).

The associated elements of DM knowledge also tended to vary by country. For instance, research have shown a link between education level and understanding about diabetes (Fenwick *et al.*, 2013; Javaeed *et al.*, 2020; Waris *et al.*, 2021).

In addition to education, additional studies have shown that people with high income levels, those who had access to diabetes educators or training, and men, all had much more knowledge about DM (Fenwick *et al.*, 2013; Alemayehu *et al.*, 2020).

The scientific community predicts a bleak future for the disease in Africa given that just US\$ 9 billion was dedicated to fighting it on the African continent in 2019 (equal to just 1% of the overall health spending for the 2019 fiscal year) (Asamoah-Boaheng *et al.*, 2019; Nomah, 2019). Therefore, it has become crucial that member nations and the international community

take unprecedented measures to ensure that the continent is free of the burden of this lethal disease.

2.3. CLASSIFICATIONS OF DIABETES MELLITUS

A categorization system's primary purpose is to serve as a guiding tool for research, evaluation of results, development of best practices for prevention and treatment, and teaching on all the aforementioned topics. However, the classification of diabetes mellitus (DM) subtypes as they are currently understood does not align with the phenotypes of diabetes (Grant *et al.*, 2010; Redondo 2013; Basile *et al.*, 2014; Leslie *et al.*, 2015; Thomas *et al.*, 2015).

The current classifications for type 1 DM, type 2 DM and latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA) are vague and hazy due to intrinsic difficulties and limited knowledge.

The late presentation of type 1 diabetes and the lack of consensus among top diabetes groups faces difficulties for the existing LADA classification scheme. (Basile *et al.*, 2014).

In fact, the measures used now are insufficient to differentiate any of the DM sub forms with clarity (Corkey 2012).

2.3.1. Insulin-dependent Diabetes Mellitus (Type 1 DM)

It is estimated that 5–10% of people with diabetes have type 1 (T1) diabetes mellitus as their underlying condition. T1 diabetes mellitus is marked by an auto-immune mechanism that causes gradually more and more pancreatic beta cells to die off until there is an utter lack of insulin. The pace of beta cell loss in T1 diabetes mellitus varies, with swift loss more common in adolescents and young adults who frequently present with diabetic ketoacidosis for the first time. T1 diabetes mellitus rates are increasing by 2% to 5% annually worldwide (Imkampe *et al.*, 2011).

T1 diabetes mellitus is most prevalent in Scandinavia, where it accounts for about 20% of all cases (American Diabetes Association, 2014). T1 diabetes typically manifests in children over 4 years old, peaking in early teenage years and puberty, with over half of newly diagnosed individuals being older than 20. Some adults may have a history of mild fasting hyperglycaemia that gradually worsens into severe hyperglycaemia and/or ketoacidosis because of coexisting diseases, indicating that exogenous insulin is now necessary to prevent ketoacidosis because residual beta cell function is no longer sufficient to do so (American Diabetes Association, 2014).

Approximately 80-90% of T1 diabetes patients have elevated titers of autoantibodies to insulin, GAD65, and IA-2 at diagnosis (American Diabetes Association, 2014). T1 diabetes mellitus has strong HLA connections, increasing the risk of developing autoimmune diseases like thyroid, Addison's, celiac, autoimmune hepatitis and pernicious anemia. Obesity does not necessarily preclude the diagnosis of Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM), even in most individuals with normal or low weight diabetes.

2.3.2. Non-insulin-dependent Diabetes Mellitus (Type 2 DM)

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) occurs when insulin resistance increases and pancreatic beta-cells produce more insulin, leading to pathological hyperglycemia (Schwartz *et al.*, 2017). T2 diabetes mellitus, affecting 90-95% of diabetes patients, ranges from insulin-resistant to insulin-independent, with early insulin therapy needed for optimal health (American Diabetes Association, 2014).

It's crucial to remember that almost all patients with T2 diabetes mellitus have some level of decreased insulin secretion at the time of diagnosis (DeFronzo, 2009). T2 diabetes mellitus is influenced by factors such as overweight and obesity, inactivity, hypertension, specific ethnic backgrounds, and dyslipidemia.

Numerous genetic risk markers have been postulated and T2 diabetes mellitus frequently runs in families, but none of them are now employed in standard clinical practice (American Diabetes Association, 2014). T2 diabetes mellitus has historically been a disease of older persons, but there is a developing outbreak of the condition in pediatric patients and young adults, that is, a reflection of rising weight gain rates. T2 diabetes mellitus in teenagers has significantly increased over the past 20-30 years, reaching 45% of cases, primarily among ethnic minority groups (American Diabetes Association, 2014).

T2 diabetes mellitus patients in Canada with early T1 or T2 diabetes had a 4-fold increased risk of renal failure despite lower initial microalbuminuria MA appearance and shorter diabetes duration (Dart *et al.*, 2012). The exact mechanisms behind the increased renal risk may be linked to increased insulin resistance (Solis-Herrera *et al.*, 2014).

The pillars of the therapy of T2DM are increased physical activity (PA) and exercise (Davies *et al.*, 2018). Aerobic fitness increases hepatic and peripheral insulin sensitivity and may enhance pancreatic beta-cell activity in individuals with T2 diabetes mellitus, according to Kirwan *et al.* (2009). Additionally, strong data suggests that sustained exercise programmes have positive impacts on people with T2DM's glycated hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) (Umpierre *et al.*, 2011).

2.3.3. Gestational Diabetes mellitus (GDM)

The diagnosis of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) usually happens during the middle or final phase of pregnancy; it is not apparent prior to conception (American Diabetes Association, 2019). The incidence of pregnancy related diabetes has considerably seen a notable rise throughout the past several decades in relation to the remarkable rise in weight gain and diabetes of type 2 (T2D). The extent of this illness is particularly influenced by ethnicity, as well as by the diagnostic standards used (Zhu & Zhang, 2016).

According to physiological principles, up until the second trimester of pregnancy, insulin sensitivity gradually diminishes, falling by 50% to 60% from pre-pregnancy levels (Baz *et al.*, 2016). Adipose tissue growth, hormone releases including progesterone and estrogen, and placental factors like human placental lactogen (hPL), all have an impact on insulin sensitivity (Baz *et al.*, 2016). Particularly, hPL has a lipolytic impact that causes the level of circulating fatty acids to increase. To provide the fetus with an appropriate glucose reserve, maternal metabolism is consequently changed to consume lipids more frequently than glucose and as a result of increased levels of maternal circulating fatty acids, insulin resistance develops (Baz *et al.*, 2016).

In this setting, production of insulin is used to counteract Central glucose resistance. Diabetes develops in the event when the rise in beta cell release is unable to offset insulin resistance. Additionally, GDM exacerbates the low-grade inflammation characterizes physiological pregnancy. Thus, this pro-inflammatory condition may lead to the development of insulin resistance (Lowe *et al.*, 2010). Body mass index (BMI) in the overweight or obese range before pregnancy, advanced maternal age, and a family history of the first-degree of type 2 diabetes are the key risk factors for GDM (Filardi *et al.*, 2018). GDM may result in a number of unfavorable pregnancy outcomes. Indeed, pre-eclampsia, and gestational hypertension are very common in moms who have GDM. GDM patients have a significantly higher caesarean section rate than women who are pregnant normally do, as well as obstetrical problems include newborn jaundice, neonatal low blood sugar, acute respiratory distress syndrome, dystocia, and preterm delivery (Xiang *et al.*, 2011; Pintaudi *et al.*, 2018). In addition to short-term problems, women with prior GDM are more likely to develop T2D, heart issues, hypertension, and GDM recurrence. Additionally, it has been shown that children of women with GDM have a higher chance of developing obesity, insulin resistance, and T2D in later life (Kelstrup *et al.*, 2013).

A one-step diagnosis process has been suggested by the International Association of the Diabetes and Pregnancy Study Groups (IADPSG). This includes measuring fasting, one-hour, and two-hour glycaemia, as well as performing an oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) using 75 g of glucose. For the purpose of making a diagnosis, one value above the threshold value at any point in time is adequate. (International Association of Diabetes, 2010). To avoid problems, the goal of treating GDM is to return overnight blood glucose levels and post-prandial glucose levels (PPG) to normal levels. Genuinely, worse pregnancy outcomes are associated with high blood glucose levels, particularly postprandial elevations (Crowther *et al.*, 2018). Education on dietary practices and way of life constitutes the initial therapeutic strategy. However, unless good glycaemic control is attained, insulin therapy is required (American Diabetes Association, 2019). Medical nutritional therapy should give the fetus enough nutrients for proper growth, but it shouldn't cause the mother to gain or lose weight (Santangelo *et al.*, 2016).

The primary cause of pregnancy weight gain is excessive energy consumption, and from 10 to 30 weeks of gestation, fuel requirements typically rise (Mousa *et al.*, 2019). Even in GDM, calorie restriction during pregnancy is not advised due to potential risks to the baby's weight. Advice for calorie consumption and weight growth should consider pre-pregnancy BMI (Mousa *et al.*, 2019). The most effective nutritional approach for GDM in terms of total calorie intake and macronutrient allocation is still up for debate (Cheung *et al.*, 2009).

2.3.4. Prediabetes

Prediabetes is defined by impaired fasting glucose (IFG) or 2-hour glucose (IGT), with WHO criteria of 6.1-6.9 mmol/L and ADA criteria of 5.6-6.9 mmol/L. The definition of prediabetes using HbA1c has received considerable attention. HbA1c 6.5% (48 mmol/mol) was added to the WHO's definition of diabetes; nevertheless, the organization found that there was insufficient data to support a HbA1c prediabetes range (World Health Organization, 2011).

The International Expert Committee (2009) and National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (2013) support using HbA1c of 6.0- 6.4%, while the American Diabetes Associations adds HbA1c of 5.7-6.4% (ADA, 2019).

2.4. RISK FACTORS OF DIABETES MELLITUS

2.4.1. Non- Modifiable Risk Factors of Diabetes

In any medical condition, there exist factors that can be altered and those that are beyond our control. Non-modifiable risk factors encompass genetics, gender, ethnicity, and age (Mekala *et al.*, 2020).

2.4.1.1. Genetics

A study conducted by Zakharova *et al.* (2019) showed that the prospect of developing diabetes of the type 1 variety in siblings of affected patients is substantially higher, about fifteen times, when compared to the risk in the general population. This strong familial association suggests a significant role for genetic factors in disease susceptibility. The genetic marker linked to type 1 diabetes is situated on chromosome 6 and is part of the HLA (human leukocyte antigen) complex. Diabetes mellitus of Type 1 has been connected to multiple HLA complexes. (Zakharova *et al.*, 2019).

Notably, type 1 diabetes often exhibits a familial clustering pattern, with first-degree relatives facing a risk 8-15 times higher than the general population, and second-degree relatives having a twofold elevated risk (Ismail *et al.*, 2020). One of the major indicators for type 1 diabetes mellitus onset is genetic predisposition. For instance, individuals with a genetic predisposition to an aggressive autoimmune response in the context of type 1 diabetes have no means to influence or manage this inherent factor (Zhou *et al.*, 2014).

2.4.1.2. Age

In contrast, certain risk factors for type 2 diabetes, such as age (being over 65) and ethnic background (African American), are beyond individual control. Typically, type 1 diabetes is diagnosed before the age of 40, although cases have been reported where illness-induced immune responses triggered diagnosis at a later age (Bered, 2022). In the United States, most type 1 diabetes diagnoses occur in children between 4 and 14 years old (Hamman *et al.*, 2014).

2.4.1.3. Ethnicity

Ethnic minorities tend to have a higher prevalence of type 1 diabetes than non-minority populations (Cherubini *et al.*, 2020). Several factors contribute to these disparities, encompassing biological and clinical factors, as well as healthcare system and social factors (Daly *et al.*, 2015). Type 1 diabetes is most prevalent among non-Hispanic Caucasians, followed by African Americans, and Hispanic Americans (Bereda *et al.*, 2022).

2.5.2. Modifiable Risk Factors of Diabetes

2.5.2.1. Pregnancy

Gestational diabetes mellitus, a pregnancy-related condition, affects 8% of US pregnancies, making it a high-risk group for type 2 diabetes development (Tobias, 2018). The prevalence of this condition is on the rise, possibly due to a combination of increasing obesity rates and the trend toward delayed motherhood (Zhang *et al.*, 2011). Compared to the entire population, women with a history of gestational diabetes are up to ten times more likely to acquire type 2 diabetes (Vounzoulaki *et al.*, 2020).

In order to prevent the development of type 2 diabetes later in life, detection of core cardiometabolic imbalance during pregnancy can diagnose gestational diabetes mellitus and enable early intervention (Zhu *et al.*, 2016). While a variety of distinct dietary and lifestyle

factors have been linked to the incidence of type 2 diabetes in these vulnerable women, more research is needed to determine how the interaction of modifiable risk factors influences the disorder's long-term risk (Hinkle et al., 2021). Furthermore, it remains to be seen if maintaining the ideal levels of these modifiable factors could lower the onset of type 2 diabetes, even among fat or overweight individuals or who have a higher hereditary susceptibility to the disease. This link is noteworthy as overweight and genetic vulnerability to type 2 diabetes are more common in women with a history of gestational diabetes mellitus (Tobias, 2018).

2.5.2.2. Obesity

Obesity is a key indicator for Type 2 Diabetes, influencing insulin resistance and disease progression, as evidenced by extensive epidemiological research (Belkina *et al.*, 2010). According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2011), nearly 90% of individuals diagnosed with diabetes are afflicted with T2DM, primarily attributable to excessive body weight. Moreover, it is worth noting that obesity often runs in families, as demonstrated by Walley *et al.* (2006).

According to Pamidi et al. (2012), obstructive sleep apnea, a sleep disease that can be treated, has a substantial negative influence on adults who are overweight or obese. It can lead to insulin resistance and glucose intolerance, which can affect 15%–30% of people with type 2 diabetes and 20%–67% of people with prediabetes (Pamidi *et al.*, 2012; Ioja *et al.*, 2012; Lindberg *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, several studies have reported a markedly higher prevalence of OSA among individuals with T2DM, ranging from 36% to 60%, compared to the general population (Schober *et al.*, 2011). These findings underscore the significance of OSA as an emerging factor in understanding the complex interplay between obesity, sleep disorders, and the development of diabetes (Schober et al., 2011).

Body Mass Index (BMI) can serve as a valuable indicator of whether one is maintaining a healthy weight or if you are in the overweight or obese category. In most cases, adults with a BMI of 25 or higher are considered overweight, which carries a greater probability of developing type 2 diabetes, as per the American Diabetes Association (2022) guidelines. However, it's worth noting that different standards apply to specific ethnic groups. For instance, Asian Americans are generally considered overweight when their BMI reaches 23 or higher, while Pacific Islanders use a threshold of 26 or higher, according to the NHLBI Obesity Education Initiative Expert Panel (2022) and Jowitt (2022).

2.5.2.3. Physical Inactivity

Lack of physical activity stands out as another significant contributor to the onset of type 2 diabetes. This can be ascribed, in part, to the inclination of inactive individuals to amass triglycerides within their muscle cells, resulting in weight gain. Physical exercise serves as a potent countermeasure against insulin resistance. Engaging in regular physical activity not only enhances the control of blood glucose levels but also diminishes the risk of developing cardiovascular complications among individuals with type 2 diabetes. As emphasized by the American Diabetes Association (ADA, 2015), consistent exercise regimens may also have a preventive effect, reducing the incidence of the disease in those deemed at high risk for the condition.

Another method to gauge the chance of getting diabetes is by measuring the waist circumference. Men with a waist circumference exceeding 40 inches have a higher diabetes chance, while non-pregnant women with a waist circumference exceeding 35 inches have an increased chance, as suggested by Cerhan *et al.* (2014). Waist circumference provides an indirect measure of abdominal fat. It is important to recognize that even if BMI falls within the

normal range, having a larger waist circumference remains a significant risk factor for both diabetes and heart disease.

2.5.2.4. Diet

Across the world, the rising prevalence of adiposity, such as overweight and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) can largely be attributed to dietary quality and excessive caloric intake (Hu *et al.*, 2011). Emerging evidence suggests that, regardless of Body Mass Index (BMI), the type of dietary fats and carbohydrates consumed plays a pivotal role in predicting the risk of diabetes (Hu *et al.*, 2011). For example, high-fiber foods like fruits and vegetables lower diabetes risk, while glycaemic load and trans-fat intake increase the risk. De Munter *et al.* (2007) conducted an illustrative meta-analysis which revealed that consuming two servings of whole grains day could potentially lower the risk of diabetes by 21%.

Research on food habits in Africa has shown a recurring trend. Frank *et al.* (2014) found that a higher incidence of type 2 diabetes is associated with inadequate fruit and vegetable eating in urban Ghana. Comparable results were noted in studies conducted on Senegalese people (Sack *et al.*, 2015) and among Nigerians (Ekpenyong *et al.*, 2012). In the North African countries, such as Egypt, diets primarily consist of high glycaemic load and high glycaemic index items, including white bread and polished rice (Hegazi *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, trans fat consumption has increased noticeably in African nations, with Egypt being one of the world's top users of these hazardous fats.

In Africa, the globalization of the food market has led to a substantial proliferation of international fast-food chains, contributing to a transition from traditional high-fiber diets to energy-dense Westernized diets (Maiyaki *et al.*, 2014). For instance, there are now over a thousand Kentucky Fried Chicken locations in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) alone, compared to

none in 1980 (Pitcher et al., 2012; Renzaho et al., 2015). Furthermore, Wojcicki et al. (2010) and Renzaho et al. (2015) estimate that there are roughly 900,000 retail Coca-Cola locations in Sub-Saharan Africa, and that 78 million servings are consumed there every day. Taking beverages with added sugar has been linked to an increased risk of type 2 diabetes (T2DM), independent of body mass index (BMI).

A recent meta-analysis found that individuals who consume one to two glasses of these beverages daily had a 26% higher risk (Hu et al., 2011). Moreover, research reveal that a 1% increase in sugar-sweetened beverage intake leads to an additional 4.8% of overweight, 2.3% of obesity, and 0.3% of diabetes people (Basu et al., 2013). Many eating practices have been connected to an increased risk of type 2 diabetes as well as an unhealthy body weight. These include consuming an excessive amount of fat overall, consuming a high intake of saturated fatty acids, and not getting enough dietary fiber (FAO, 2010; Ley et al., 2014; WHO, 2015). While fruit and vegetable availability in many African countries is seasonal, the globalization of the food market has the potential to enhance their accessibility. However, in most countries, easy access to these healthy foods is associated with higher socioeconomic positions, ultimately influencing their consumption (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2006).

Notably, children in Australia diagnosed with type 1 diabetes tend to follow diets characterized by elevated sodium and saturated fat intake (Adams *et al.*, 2017; Bereda, 2022). Additionally, there is a growing concern surrounding shifts in early childhood dietary habits, as the incidence of type 1 diabetes has seen its most significant rise among the youngest age groups (Zhou *et al.*, 2021). These findings emphasize the need for further research and public health initiatives aimed at encouraging healthier dietary choices and better infant feeding practices to reduce the risk of developing type 1 diabetes (Zhou *et al.*, 2021).

2.5.2.5. Alcohol

Alcohol consumption constitutes a significant contributor to premature mortality and disability (Bissessu *et al.*, 2009). A systematic review conducted by Howard *et al.* (2004) reported that moderate alcohol intake is linked to a reduced risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). However, it is worth noting that alcohol misuse significantly exacerbates adiposity and abdominal obesity across all genders.

In various African nations, including Nigeria (Puepet *et al.*, 2008), Kenya (Christensen, 2009), South Africa (Motala, 2008), and others such as those examined by Tuei *et al.* (2010), there have been diverse findings regarding the association between alcohol consumption and diabetes. Some studies have indeed established a strong connection between alcohol abuse and the incidence of diabetes (Tuei *et al.*, 2010). A variety of African population segments have reported these findings, including rural South Africa (Motala *et al.*, 2008), Kenya (Christensen *et al.*, 2009), and Nigeria (Etukumana *et al.*, 2014).

Throughout Africa, alcohol use is very common, with the exception of areas where it is illegal. Alcohol is a significant cultural, traditional, customary, and social element in many African civilizations, with a long and rich history (Mayige *et al.*, 2012). Western alcoholic beverages, while costly, carry cultural and economic importance due to their prestigious status (Obot *et al.*, 2006). Typically reserved for traditional gatherings and significant events (Obot *et al.*, 2006), they are, however, complemented by locally produced and more affordable alcoholic beverages like ogogoro in Nigeria, burukutu and pito (or illicit gin-like drinks) in Zambia and Ghana, and Gongo in Tanzania (Obot *et al.*, 2006).

2.5.2.6. Tobacco

Tobacco use, whether smoking or smokeless, is highly linked to a greater likelihood of type 2 diabetes mellitus, manifesting either independently or in combination with as central obesity.

(Melikian *et al.*, 2009). Smokeless tobacco products, derived from the *Nicotiana tabacum* plant are notably more affordable than cigarettes, making them a preferred choice among individuals with lower socioeconomic status (WHO, 2011). These products can be consumed by smoking, chewing, or snuffing.

In 2007, Willi *et al.*'s 2007 systematic review found that smokers have a 45% higher risk of acquiring diabetes, especially in men in sub-Saharan Africa and North Africa (Willi *et al.*, 2007). Adult males in Egypt nearly 39.7% smoke, making it a country with a significant adult male smoking population (Hegazi *et al.* 2015). Studies show traditional smokeless tobacco contains higher levels of carcinogenic nitrosamines than commercially manufactured cigarettes, despite limited data on their toxicities in Africa (WHO, 2013; 2017). Additionally, studies done in South Africa have demonstrated that women who smoke heavily run a higher risk of diabetes (WHO, 2017; National Cancer Institute and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2018).

2.5.2.7. Physical stress

Physical stress can trigger the release of hormones such as adrenaline and cortisol into the bloodstream (Bereda *et al.*, 2022) and when released, have the potential to elevate blood glucose levels. Stress is, therefore, a potential factor contributing to sustained high blood sugar levels in individuals with diabetes and the profound impact of stress on metabolic processes has long been established, as indicated by the research of Kang *et al.* (2020).

One of the primary consequences of the body's response to stress, often referred to as the "fight or flight" response, is the mobilization of energy resources. When an individual experiences stress, the body takes measures to ensure an adequate supply of sugar or energy is readily available (Romero *et al.*, 2022). This response includes a decrease in insulin levels, an increase

in glucagon and epinephrine (adrenaline) levels, and the release of additional glucose from the liver (Qaid *et al.*, 2016).

2.6. DIABETES MANAGEMENT

With a sharp rise in patients in both industrialized and developing nations, type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) is seen as a spreading pandemic (Jayawardena *et al.*, 2012; Nanditha *et al.*, 2016; Yang *et al.*, 2016). Since DM pandemic is believed to be caused by a multitude of variables, such as increased obesity prevalence, population aging, and longer lifespans because of enhanced medical and its consequences have a significant worldwide impact, it is obvious that effective strategies for mass-scale disease prevention are required (Jayawardena *et al.*, 2012; Nanditha *et al.*, 2016; Yang *et al.*, 2016).

2.6.1. Weight Management

Recent research on obese individuals undergoing gastric bypass surgery, metabolic irregularities associated with type 2 diabetes can be corrected, and diabetic drugs may be stopped shortly after the treatment (Nguyen & Varela, 2017).

The restoration of plasma glucose concentrations within the first week after surgery has been linked to calorie restriction during the post-operative phase (Isbell *et al.*, 2010; Lips *et al.*, 2014; Batterham & Cummings, 2016). Studies show that a Very-Low-Calorie Diet (VLCD) can significantly improve glycaemic control in individuals with type 2 diabetes (Baker *et al.*, 2009; Malandrucco *et al.*, 2012; Lean *et al.*, 2018).

One week following VLCD, patients with extreme obesity (body mass index [BMI] of 30 kg/m²) showed an improvement in liver glucose tolerance; nevertheless, the inability of beta cells to release insulin was recovered within eight weeks. (Lim *et al.*, 2011). However, in patients with excessive weight (BMI 45 kg/m²), there was only an increase in insulin secretion

and no alteration in the sensitivity of the liver to insulin (Malandrucco et al., 2012). Those who dropped more weight tended to have a higher rate of diabetes remission (Steven et al., 2013). All these findings point to the possibility that VLCD can correct the pathophysiologic flaws that underlie type 2 diabetes (Lim et al., 2011; Malandrucco et al., 2012; Steven & Taylor, 2015; Steven et al., 2016). But practically all VLCD trials have been carried out on people of European ancestry with high BMI. Comparatively to their European counterparts, Asians with type 2 DM often have lower BMI and more significant beta cell dysfunction (Ma & Chan, 2013).

2.6.2. Medication

Over the last four decades, there has been extensive research into the application of continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII) as a basic therapy for individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (Type 2 DM), including those who have recently been diagnosed with the condition. This approach has been explored across various patient groups, even encompassing those with suboptimal glycaemic control (Pickup, 2014).

From 2008 to 2013, several uncontrolled studies delved into insulin pump therapy (CSII) for Type 2 diabetes patients. The investigations consistently demonstrated that transitioning to CSII therapy boosted glucose regulation, reduced routine insulin requirements, and increased patient fulfilment contrary to conventional Multiple Dose Injection therapy (MDI) (Gentry *et al.*, 2011). These investigations were conducted in diverse settings, including clinical research centers, hospital outpatient clinics, and small private outpatient offices.

In recent years, numerous studies have concentrated on the use of Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) in individuals with Type 2 DM. These studies primarily focused on the efficacy of CGM in managing hypoglycemia and reducing glucose variability (Carlson *et al.*, 2017). A notable study by Vigersky *et al.* (2017), examined patients using dietary and lifestyle

interventions, alone or in combination with oral agent therapy, with or without basal insulin. The study revealed a noteworthy reduction in mean unadjusted HbA1C levels of 1.0% versus 0.5% at week 12 and 0.8% versus 0.2% at week 52 when compared to the Self-Monitoring of Blood Glucose (SMBG) group. Importantly, the improvements were achieved without the need for medication intensification or an increase in hypoglycaemic events (Carlson *et al.*, 2017). Another study highlighted that even intermittent CGM usage could serve as a valuable motivational tool and help prevent "burnout" among individuals with Type 2 DM (Graham *et al.*, 2016; Vigersky *et al.*, 2017).

In December 2017, a significant milestone was achieved with the FDA's approval of the first smart pen system in the United States. This innovative insulin pen system not only records insulin doses and injection times but also wirelessly transmits this data to a mobile application installed on the patient's smartphone. The mobile app boasts dose calculation capabilities, allowing for the precise delivery of insulin in less than whole-number units, a feature conventional insulin pens cannot provide (FDA, 2017). Collectively, these studies, both historical and ongoing, consistently highlight the potential benefits of CGM utilization in individuals with Type 2 DM. These benefits include improvements in A1C levels, the ability to detect hypoglycemia risks, particularly during nighttime hours when they might not be clinically evident, and the capacity to assess and address glucose fluctuations.

2.6.3. Dietary Management

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2017) and Yang *et al.* (2015), almost two-thirds of the US populace is overweight or obese, which is also related to the increased prevalence of type 2 diabetes. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 30.3 million Americans had type 2 diabetes as of 2017, and by 2050, up to one-third of Americans are expected to have the disease (Boyle *et al.*, 2020).

A small amount of loss in weight and lifestyle modifications can improve glycaemia in diabetic individuals and stop prediabetes from progressing to type 2 diabetes. Such measures often involve changes in diet, physical activity, and antihyperglycemic drugs. Due to the wide variety of diets utilized in prior research (Ley *et al.*, 2014; Terranova *et al.*, 2015; Schwingshackl *et al.*, 2018), the ideal diet to promote weight reduction and enhance glycaemic control is still unknown. In the intensive treatment arm, for example, the United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study recommended a diet low in calories (50%–55% carbohydrates, 30%–35% fat, 10%–15% protein), either with or no enhanced care using insulin, metformin, and/or sulfonylurea medicines. Despite reporting calorie consumption below required and an average 0.9% reduction in A1C in the intensive therapy arm compared to the usual treatment arm, respondents' mean weight rose to 2.9 kg at trial's end (Terranova *et al.*, 2015).

The ADA recommends personalized meal plans with nutrient-rich foods, low-refined starchy foods, and high-saturated fats, but precise protein, carbohydrate, and lipid amounts are not yet established (ADA, 2019). Low carbohydrate, high fat (LCHF) diets have shown promise in improving glycaemia and weight loss in randomized controlled trials and observational research, and frequently do so while lowering the number and/or doses of antidiabetic drugs (Paoli *et al.*, 2013; Tay *et al.*, 2015; Goday *et al.*, 2016; Thompson *et al.*, 2018). While there are not enough permanent coronary artery disease outcome examinations, the Low

Carbohydrate High Fiber diet can potentially lower cardiovascular risk and improve cardiometabolic parameters like total cholesterol to HDL-C, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol particle size, apolipoprotein (Apo) B to Apo A1 ratio, and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL) (Hu et al., 2012; Guay et al., 2012).

In a recent update to its lifestyle management recommendations, the American Diabetes Association (ADA) noted that individuals with hyperglycemia who wish to wean themselves off of glucose-lowering medications can achieve this by following a very low carbohydrate diet (ADA, 2019).

Although the Low Carbohydrate, High Fiber diet has received positive feedback, its exact influence on digestion remains not known due to the fact that earlier studies had varying amounts of macro-nutrients; for example, carbohydrates may account for up to 40% of total calories, which could mitigate its effects (Davis et al., 2009; Tay et al., 2018). Even after a year, a trial conducted remotely with a more stringent definition of reduced carbohydrate (5–10% of total calories) yielded very positive results (Hallberg et al., 2018).

Carbohydrates (CHOs), though constitute a significant source of energy, they are more likely than other macronutrients to cause an increase in post-meal hyperglycaemia (Reader, 2007). Moderation of CHO consumption is beneficial in diabetes mellitus, as higher CHO ratios lead to elevated postprandial glucose. However, limiting CHO is not necessary; slowing down CHO digestion and absorption can prevent abnormal glucose increases. The length of the CHO polymer affects how food is absorbed and digested, which may help keep blood glucose levels from rising after eating.

Measures of the impact of various diets on glycaemia include glycaemic response (GR), glycaemic index (GI), and glycaemic load (GL) (Augustin *et al.*, 2015). The glycaemic response is the post-prandial glucose fluctuation brought on by consuming a diet containing CHO (Augustin *et al.*, 2015). The glycaemic load is the glycaemic response of a serving of

food with 50 g of accessible CHO, calculated as a percentage of the reference CHO (Augustin *et al.*, 2015). Rice and potatoes have a high glycaemic index due to their rapid glycaemia rise, while fruits and dairy products have a low glycaemic index due to slow digestion (Augustin *et al.*, 2015; Musa *et al.*, 2019).

High glycaemic index (GI) foods have a GI above 70, containing CHOs, which are quickly metabolized and digested. Low GI foods are below 55 and take longer to digest. The glycaemic index measures glycaemic response and caliber of CHOs. The glycaemic load gauges both quantity and quality of CHOs (Augustin *et al.*, 2015).

The glycaemic load (GL) allows comparison of whole diets, meals, and foods based on their impact (Augustin *et al.*, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2019). International tables and the International Organization for Standardization's reference approach are available, expanding its application to include mixed meals and complete diets (Augustin *et al.*, 2015; IOS, 2019).

Another crucial determinant of diet quality is the presence of dietary fibers (DF), which are plant-based CHO that cannot be digested (Aziz, 2009). Fruits, vegetables, and legumes all contain soluble dietary fiber. Dietary fiber that is soluble slows down digestion and lowers cholesterol and postprandial glucose absorption. Nuts, wholegrain bread, and cereals all include insoluble dietary fibers. Resistant starch can be found in cooked potatoes and rice (Mousa *et al.*, 2019). Resistant starch and insoluble DF have few metabolic effects (Ludwig *et al.*, 2019).

2.6.3. Lifestyle and Physical Activity

Due to the requirement for daily self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) levels and prompt writing of these in a logbook, managing T1 diabetes is a significant problem in resource-constrained low- and medium-income nations (Patterson *et al.*, 2014; Kesavadev *et al.*, 2014).

As per the American Diabetes Association (2016), all patients with type 1 diabetes (T1DM),

type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), or any other type of diabetes that requires frequent subcutaneous insulin injections are advised to use SMBG.

A study found that higher daily SMBG intake significantly reduces HbA1c levels in children and adolescents with T1diabetes, and reduces acute problems like ketoacidosis (Selvan et al., 2017).

It has been demonstrated that using cutting-edge mobile phone applications and routine self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) will boost compliance with suggested treatment regimens (Klienman *et al.*, 2017). Increasing daily activity by 1000 steps can dramatically lower the incidence of cardiovascular events in people with type 1 diabetes (Anderson *et al.*, 2016). The fit-bit-app is a wireless wearable electronic gadget that records data in a mobile phone application to track steps taken (Diaz *et al.*, 2015; Evenson *et al.*, 2015; Coughlin *et al.*, 2017). Studies done in Pakistan show astounding rates of problems such diabetic acidosis as a result of inadequate care, including non-adherence of T1diabetic patients to food guidance (58.5%), recommendations regarding physical activity (42.3%), and recommended insulin regimens (88.1%) (Lone *et al.*, 2010; Riaz *et al.*, 2014).

In several investigations on T1diabetes patients, compliance to management guidelines and insulin regimens exhibited an adverse relationship with the development of acute complications (Realsen *et al.*, 2015). Patients with type 1 diabetes in Pakistan who had poor compliance with their insulin regimen or had none at all required extended hospital admissions due to the severity of their diabetic ketoacidosis (Syed *et al.*, 2015). Teenagers with T1 diabetes showed significant changes in behavior and supervision after receiving family-centered care, allowing family members to maintain records of blood glucose levels, insulin dosage, physical activity, and food plan (Cheraghi *et al.*, 2015).

T1 diabetes management is a major difficulty at the regional level since doctors rarely follow the global treatment recommendations (Kesavadev *et al.*, 2014; Coughlin *et al.*, 2017). There

are several electronic gadgets that can track physical activity, and they have all been researched for use by diabetic patients globally (Evenson *et al.*, 2015; Coughlin *et al.*, 2017; Selvan *et al.*, 2017). Due to the high prevalence of T2 diabetes, the majority of studies using an electronic device to improve patient outcomes have been conducted on T2 diabetic patients (Meyer *et al.*, 2013; Vaes *et al.*, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2015; Miyauchi *et al.*, 2016). T1 diabetes patients, typically pediatrics, face increased risk of severe complications, necessitating multifaceted approaches involving patients, parents, families, physicians, and stakeholders for optimal management (Lone *et al.*, 2010; Syed *et al.*, 2011; Riaz *et al.*, 2014; Anderzén *et al.*, 2015; Basit *et al.*, 2015).

In T1-diabetic children aged 11.54 ± 4.05 years, an Indian study indicated that precise SMBG logs dramatically lowered HbA1c levels from $10.79 \pm 2.61\%$ to $7.99 \pm 0.84\%$, while faulty logs caused a reduction in HbA1c levels from $10.74 \pm 2.60\%$ to $9.01 \pm 2.33\%$ during a four-month period (Selvan *et al.*, 2017).

2.7. KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICES OF DIABETICS

According to Marathe *et al.* (2016), Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) studies are frequently used to gather data on a certain condition and determine what people know (Knowledge), feel (Attitude), and practice (Practice) (du Monde, 2016). Not only are knowledge, attitude, and practice related, but knowledge and attitude also have a direct impact on preventive practice (International Diabetes Federation, 2015).

KAP studies can be used for many different themes and health-related topics (du Monde, 2016). KAP studies have several appealing features, such as a straightforward study design, quantifiable data, succinct results that are simple to interpret. In addition, it has the ability to generalize the findings from a small sample to the entire population when done correctly, cross-cultural comparability, and a rapid implementation process (Marathe *et al.*, 2016).

According to du Monde (2016), KAP studies are useful for planning and designing appropriate, cost-effective, and targeted intervention programmes as well as for measuring the impact of an intervention by comparing baseline and end-line values to assess the efficacy of health promotion and education activities or interventions that have the potential to alter health-related behaviors. However, because of the scarcity of scientific data on the proper markers to evaluate KAP in the research across the global health community, several social scientists have disputed the accuracy of information and application of KAP studies (Du Monde, 2016).

Numerous research endeavors have been undertaken to evaluate the understanding, stance, and conduct of individuals dealing with diabetes. In the United Arab Emirates, a study discovered that 76% of diabetes patients were unable to distinguish between foods with low and high glycaemic carbohydrates. This underscores a notable deficiency in knowledge among patients in this particular region (Al-Maskari *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, a study conducted in Kenya found that only 30.2% of individuals exhibited a strong grasp of diabetes, indicating a dearth of awareness and comprehension of the disease among this group (Maina *et al.*, 2010).

The outlook of patients toward diabetes also carries significant weight in the management of the condition. A study in the Saurashtra region of Gujarat revealed that many patients harbored negative attitudes toward diabetes. Such pessimistic attitudes can impede patients from embracing healthier lifestyles and adhering to treatment regimens. It is imperative to confront these negative sentiments and provide patients with the requisite support and education to encourage positive changes in their behavior (Shah *et al.*, 2009; Maina *et al.*, 2010).

The behavior and practices of individuals with diabetes constitute another crucial facet to consider. Research indicates that a considerable number of patients struggle to adhere to their prescribed treatment plans and find it challenging to adopt necessary lifestyle modifications. Such non-adherence can result in suboptimal glycaemic control and heightened risks of complications. It is indispensable to equip patients with the necessary resources and guidance

to effectively manage their diabetes while motivating them to embrace healthier practices (Shah *et al.*, 2009).

A study conducted in rural Sullia, Karnataka, India, involving 400 participants and employed a cross-sectional design to evaluate the understanding of individuals living with diabetes regarding diabetes and self-care. The findings revealed that only 25% of the participants, amounting to 100 individuals, possessed adequate knowledge about diabetes. Alarmingly, a significant number of them demonstrated poor adherence to diabetes self-care practices, including diet, regular exercise, and daily foot inspections. However, it is important to note that this study had certain limitations, such as the use of closed-ended questionnaires, which may have led to responses based on guesswork (Dinesh *et al.*, 2016).

In the realm of diabetes care, it is widely recognized as a collective responsibility. Nevertheless, existing literature consistently highlights the inadequacy of knowledge about diabetes and diabetes care among patients with diabetes. A study conducted in Pakistan among 100 respondents aimed to assess their knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to diabetes. The results revealed that approximately 54% of the participants had limited knowledge of diabetes, with only 13% displaying a commendable understanding of diabetes and its management (Badrudin *et al.*, 2002). This phenomenon could be attributed to healthcare providers' focus on medication administration without comprehensive patient education or follow-up once they leave healthcare facilities (Adams & Carter, 2011).

Another study, carried out in the rural areas of Sangli District, Maharashtra, India, involving 307 participants and employing a cross-sectional design, also uncovered insufficient knowledge about diabetes. This insufficiency was linked to poor knowledge of diabetes care, however, it is important to consider that compliance among diabetes patients was evaluated without direct verification, possibly leading to overestimation (Chavan *et al.*, 2018).

Additionally, research has consistently shown that individuals with diabetes often lack substantial knowledge about their condition (Formosa & Muscat, 2016), a sentiment echoed in a study conducted in Zimbabwe (Mufunda and Ernersson, 2018). However, some studies dispute the notion that diabetes patients universally possess inadequate knowledge (Al-ghamdi *et al.*, 2018).

Interestingly, while diabetes knowledge does not always significantly correlate with self-care practices (Formosa & Muscat, 2016), Carole *et al.* (2016) emphasized the positive impact of diabetes self-care education on self-management and glycaemic control (Chrvala *et al.*, 2016). They asserted that factors such as engagement hours, delivery methods, and baseline A1C levels can significantly influence glycaemic control in a positive manner (Chrvala *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, improving diabetes patients' knowledge of self-care may necessitate healthcare providers' active involvement during consultations (Umeh & Nkombua, 2018).

Patients' attitudes towards diabetes and diabetes care are influenced by various factors, including the behaviour of healthcare providers. A qualitative study utilizing a focus group approach, conducted in Queen Elizabeth Hospital, explored patients' perceptions of the quality of care. The feedback highlighted that patient expectations were often unmet, with care providers failing to conduct examinations, run laboratory tests, or provide sufficient education on the benefits of diabetes care. Additionally, challenges such as busy working hours, long wait times, and difficulties in making time for diabetes tests and care were cited. Some patients found it challenging to change their behavior, especially regarding their preference for sweet foods, which hindered adherence to diabetes care (Adams & Carter, 2011).

A common belief among patients is that diabetes is an expensive condition to manage, encompassing high costs for medications, fruits, vegetables, and other necessities. This perception can drive some individuals towards herbal remedies as a more affordable alternative (Shah *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, a study revealed that a significant percentage (79.63%) of

respondents struggled with poor adherence to exercise regimens (Umeh & Nkombua, 2018). Additionally, research has shown that patients' attitudes are associated with their self-care practices (Timothy Chas Skinner, 2015).

Patients with diabetes hold a variety of beliefs about the condition and its management. In Barbados, a focus group study was conducted to explore the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and barriers experienced by individuals with diabetes and hypertension. The results revealed differing perceptions, with some patients feeling well-treated by their healthcare providers, while others perceived a lack of attention and respect. Some patients also expressed concerns about the high costs associated with diabetes care and noted deficiencies in customer relations at public health facilities and pharmacies (Adams & Carter, 2011).

Moreover, the social networks in which individuals with diabetes find themselves play a pivotal role in determining their adherence to self-management. Social support networks and personal beliefs significantly influence self-care practices and contribute to social solidarity, ensuring sustained care, management, and overall well-being (Timothy Chas Skinner, 2015). Similarly, research conducted indicated that healthcare providers' consultations with diabetes patients can enhance their knowledge and self-management capabilities (Umeh & Nkombua, 2018). Additionally, a study in Saudi Arabia found that individuals with diabetes generally hold positive perceptions of diabetes and its management (Al-ghamdi *et al.*, 2018). These positive attitudes have been shown to correlate with improved adherence to self-care practices (Timothy Chas Skinner, 2015).

In summary, existing literature consistently suggests a positive correlation between diabetes patients' knowledge, attitudes, and self-care practices, with better knowledge leading to better adherence and poor knowledge resulting in sub optimal self-care. However, it is important to recognize that individual experiences and circumstances may vary. Positive attitudes and beliefs towards diabetes also play a crucial role in promoting adherence to self-care practices.

In conclusion, the knowledge, attitude, and practices of diabetes patients are pivotal in the effective management of the disease and the prevention of complications. The research underscores a noteworthy deficit in patient knowledge, underscoring the urgency of enhancing education and awareness. Tackling negative attitudes and extending support to patients can foster constructive behavioral changes. Additionally, promoting adherence to treatment plans and encouraging the adoption of healthy practices are essential for achieving optimal diabetes management. By addressing these aspects, healthcare professionals can empower patients to take charge of their diabetes and enhance their overall health outcomes.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1. STUDY DESIGN

This research utilized a descriptive cross-sectional design to assess the presence and associated factors of a specific disease or condition within a specific population at specific time intervals. The study was carried out within five months from September 2022 to January 2023. The sample was collected from the Enyiresi Government Hospital, Enyiresi in the Eastern Region of Ghana.

3.2. STUDY AREA

The study area was Enyiresi Government Hospital located at Akyem Enyiresi in the Eastern Region of Ghana. The area is located in the Atiwa East district of Akyem and situated between Anyinam and Sekyere town on the Accra-Kumasi Road. The multidisciplinary facility where the study is being conducted offers primary and secondary care to patients in need of general and specialized medical services. It consists of specially designed inpatient and outpatient facilities, as well as a weekly Thursday and Friday Diabetes Clinic Unit. The hospital is the biggest district hospital to which patients from every part of the district are referred to for expert medical treatment.

3.3. STUDY POPULATION

The study population were known patients with type 1 or 2 diabetes, adult age 18 years and older who lived in neighboring towns and visited the Enyiresi Government hospital, Akyem Enyiresi for their clinicals during the study period. The people of Enyiresi are ethnically Akyem and widely known to be very resourceful and hardworking. They are mainly traders, subsistence farmers, hairdressers, teachers, drivers, carpenters, masons, office workers,

mechanics, and others. The vernacular spoken is Akyem Twi, but English is also widely used as a generic language for administrative and economic transactions. All classes and categories of people inhabit this town and its neighboring commercial towns.

3.4. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

3.4.1. Inclusion criteria

- The study population were patients with both type 1 & 2 DM who visited Enyiresi Government Hospital.
- Individuals, regardless of gender, confirmed with type 1 or type 2 diabetes at least six months prior and aged 18 or older.
- Individuals were considered eligible if they gave their verbal approval and agreed to answer the questionnaire's questions.

3.4.2. Exclusion Criteria

- Criteria for exclusion were participants who were diabetic but less than 18 years.
- Participants with gestational diabetes, or unspecified type of diabetes were also excluded.
- Visiting patients who were not regular patients for the hospital were excluded as well.
- Patients with diabetes related complications like renal failure, severe heart or liver diseases were excluded from the study.
- Patients who did not give their consent.

3.5. SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

The sample quantity was determined using a single population proportion formula, aiming for 90% of the population with 95% confidence intervals and 5% margin error.

$$n = z^2 p (1 - p) / w^2,$$

Where n = sample size

p = proportion (90%)

w = margin of error (5%)

z-score = 1.96 confidence level

$$n = 1.962 \times 0.9 (1-0.9) / 0.05^2$$

$$n = 3.84 \times 0.9 (0.1) / 0.0025$$

$$n = 0.3456 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 138$$

The researcher populated the sample size with an additional 12. This was to cover in for any none or missing responses. This brought the total sample size for the present study to 150.

3.6. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The sampling techniques used were purposive and random sample. Purposive sample for participant that fit the inclusion criteria and random sampling for selection of the participants.

3.7. DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUES AND TOOLS

The study utilized a questionnaire to assess diabetes patients' understanding, mindset, and habits. Relevant literature was used to inform the questionnaire's questions (Rahaman et al., 2017; Belsti et al., 2020). It collected socio-demographic data, including age, gender, height, weight, marital status, education, and income. The questionnaire also assessed the patients' BMI using height and weight, duration since diagnosis, health insurance, and participation in diabetes education programs.

3.7.1. Knowledge, Attitude and Practices

Regardless of their actual practices, the patients were asked to respond to the knowledge-related questions. The patients were questioned about the tests used to diagnose diabetes

mellitus, the measures that may be taken to manage the condition, the length of time that patients should stick to their diet and treatment plans, and the organs that diabetes mellitus may damage.

Regardless of their practices, the patients were asked to respond to the questions about attitude. Attitude questions included how often they ate fast foods, how often they ate fruits and vegetables in the course of the week, whether only diet without their medication can help reduce their blood glucose levels, whether eating of certain herbs like ginger, garlic, and others can reduce their blood glucose levels rather than adhering to diet and medication, whether exercise alone can lower their blood glucose levels and whether the patients should go for regular check-ups even if their blood glucose was under control or not and are suffering from complications or not .

The patients were asked to respond to questions about practice that were pertinent to their real practices. Practice questions included the following: can the patients encourage their family members with diabetes to seek treatment; can they follow the recommendations of their compassionate healthcare providers regarding regular exercise (30–60 minutes per week); can they check their blood sugar levels on a regular basis; and can they successfully avoid refined or processed foods as much as possible?

3.7.2. Anthropometry

Respondents' weight was recorded numerically to the nearest 0.1 kg for anthropometric measurements. The numerical scale was set to 0.00 before each recording. Height (cm) was measured on a calibrated digital scale (Jactermac, ZT-150A) with bare, minimally clad, and shoeless participants. Body mass index was calculated using the weight-for-height equation (kg/m^2), and the threshold value for normal is 18.5–24.9 kg/m^2 , 25.0–29 for overweight and greater than or equal to 30.0 kg/m^2 for obesity.

3.8. DATA ANALYSIS

Data were examined for precision and completeness in the current investigation, and any missing, erroneous, or incomplete replies were omitted. The collected submissions were summarized, coded, and tabulated. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and presented using percentages, tables of frequency and charts for quicker comprehension and interpretation. The relationship between variables were determined using Pearson correlation. Correlation tests and correlations between descriptive variables and results of interest were conducted using the chi-square test.

3.9. ETHICAL APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

The CHPRE of College of Science, School of Medicine and Dentistry at the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology granted ethical approval with reference number (Research project reference number: CHRPE/AP/727/22) prior to data collection. Before allowing potential participants to participate in the current study, the field investigators verbally informed them of its purpose and goals and got their agreement. Written consent for this study was approved by Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology's CHRPE. The Ministry of Health granted permission to enter the healthcare facility. Patients who matched the criteria for this study were enrolled upon giving informed permission and receiving confidentiality guarantees for research purposes.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the results of the findings from the study data. The results of the study are presented according to the objectives and research questions.

4.2. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

The results showed that majority (56%) of the respondents were females while 44% were males. Diabetes among the age group showed that individual in the age range of 41-50 years had the highest rate of 38%, followed by those above 50 years with 34%, then those aged between 31-40 with 28% and there was no indication among those between 20-30 years. The results showed that the majority 69% of diabetics were married, 39% were widowed while 21% were either single or divorced. Respondents with basic school education were 42%, followed by secondary education respondents with 34%, while non-formal and tertiary education respondents were 20% and 4%, respectively. Regarding the average income of the respondents, 38% were earning between GHC 501-800, 28% between GHC 201-500, while 20% between GHC 801-1000.

From the results 64% indicated they had relatives with history of diabetes while 18% each indicated they either had no relative with diabetes history or do not know. Similarly, 34% indicated they had relatives with Type 2 diabetes and 26% with Type 1 diabetes, while majority (40%) did not know about the type of diabetes affecting their relatives.

Table 4.1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=150)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	66	44
Female	84	56
Age groups		
31-40	42	28
41-50	57	38
Above 51	51	34
Marital status		
Single	14	21
Married	46	69
Divorced	14	21
Widowed	26	39
Level of education		
Non-formal	30	20
Basic	63	42
Secondary	51	34
Tertiary	6	4
Average income		
<200	12	8
201-500	42	28
501-800	57	38
801-1000	30	20
>1000	9	6
Family history of diabetes		
Type 1	39	26
Type 2	51	34
Don't know	60	40

4.3. BMI STATUS AMONG THE DIABETES PATIENTS

As presented in Table 4.2, the mean weight and height of the respondents were 64.03 ± 9.46 and 154.65 ± 8.65 , respectively. Again, about 1.3% of the respondents were underweight while majority (55.4%) were overweight/obese. Additionally, about 43.3% of the respondents were normal. The mean BMI of the respondents was 27.07 ± 5.47 .

Table 4.2: BMI Status Among the Diabetes Patients

Variables (BMI)	Frequency (n=150)	Percentage (%)
Nutritional status		
Underweight	2	1.3
Normal	65	43.3
overweight	37	24.7
obese	46	30.7
	Mean	Standard deviation
Weight	64.03	9.46
Height	154.65	8.65
BMI	27.07	5.47

Source: WHO, 2016

4.4. KNOWLEDGE OF DIABETES AMONG RESPONDENTS

From Table 4.3, the respondents expressed their knowledge on diabetes. Majority (95.3%) of the respondents indicated that blood glucose increases when someone has diabetes. 30% of participants were aware the condition is incurable, more than three-quarters (90%) understood it affects other organs, and 64% knew blood glucose measurement after fasting is the best way to confirm the disease.

Table 4.3: Knowledge on Diabetes

Variables (BMI)	Frequency (n=150)	Percentage (%)
What happens to blood glucose in diabetes?		
	3	2.0
Decreases	4	2.7
Do not know	143	95.3
Increases		
Is diabetes curable with treatment?		
Yes	8	5.3
No	45	30.0
Do not know	97	64.7
Do you think diabetes can affect other organs?		
Yes	141	94.0
No	6	4.0
Do not know	3	2.0
What is the best way to diagnose Diabetes?		
a) Measuring blood glucose after fasting is the best way to diagnose diabetes	96	64.0
b) Measuring urine glucose is the best way to diagnose diabetes	54	36.0

From Figure 4.1, it was found that 88%, forming the majority of the respondents, were of the view that diabetes is mostly caused by eating too much sugar, lack of insulin (83%), failure of the body to use insulin (71%), followed by sedentary lifestyle (65%). Stress (43%) was the least cause of diabetes.

Figure 4.1: Respondents' Knowledge on the Causes of Diabetes

From Figure 4.2, it was found that 89% of the respondents knew frequent urination as a symptom of diabetes followed by increased thirst (88%), loss of appetite/weight loss (71%), abdominal pains (61%) and slow healing process (58%).

Figure 4.2: Respondents knowledge on the symptoms of diabetes

The most effective therapy used in the control of blood sugar identified by this study were the avoidance of sugary food (63%), oral medication (92%), and regular exercise (71%). Insulin injection (88%) and regular eating of some herbs such as garlic, ginger and others (43%) were also reported to be therapies for the control of diabetes (Figure 4.2).

From Figure 4.4, 85% of the respondents indicated that diabetes can lead to stroke, followed by heart attack (76%), kidney failure (71%), loss of vision (65%) and amputation (59%).

Figure 4.3: Respondents' Knowledge on Therapies for Effective Control of Blood Glucose

Figure 4.4: Respondents' Knowledge on the Effects of Diabetes

4.5. ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES ON DIABETES AMONG DIABETES PATIENTS

Table 4.5 showed the attitude and practices among respondents. Majority (70.7%) of the respondents believed that blood glucose could be controlled with only diet. Over half (54.0%) of respondents believe ginger, cinnamon, and fenugreek are better than prescribed drugs for treating the diseases, while 33.3% prefer alternative therapies like acupuncture, yoga, hypnosis,

relaxation exercises, or herbal remedies to diet control and medication. Again, about 92.7% of the respondents stated that they would consider treatment if family members had diabetes. Additionally, more than half (55.3%) of the respondents engaged in about 30-60 minutes physical activity daily such as brisk walking, house activities, climbing staircase. A significant proportion (30.0%) of the respondents did check blood glucose regularly while 59.3% of the remaining sometimes checked their blood sugar. Meanwhile, about 36.7% of the respondents stated they try to avoid refine glucose/sugary foods outright because of their condition (Table 4.4).

Table 4.4: Diabetes Patients' Attitude and Practices

Variables	Frequency (n=150)	Percentage (%)
Controlling glucose with diet and medications		
Do not know	9	6.0
No	35	23.3
Yes	106	70.7
Ginger, cinnamon, and fenugreek are better for treating diabetes than prescription drugs		
Do not know	10	6.7
No	59	39.3
Yes	81	54.0
Alternative therapies		
Do not know	13	8.7
No	87	58.0
Yes	50	33.3
Consider treatment because of family history		
Maybe	11	7.3
Yes	139	92.7
Physical activity daily		
Maybe	8	5.4
No	3	2.0
Sometimes	56	37.3
Yes	83	55.3
Check blood sugar regularly		
Maybe	6	4.0
No	10	6.7
Sometimes	89	59.3
Yes	45	30.0
Avoid refine sugar/sugary foods		
Maybe	8	5.4
No	6	4.0
Sometimes	81	54.0
Yes	55	36.7

4.6. KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE SCORES ON DIABETES

Table 4.5 presents a comprehensive overview of the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) scores among the study participants with respect to diabetes. This study's KAP score was based on a study conducted by Reid *et al.* (2019) and Muhammad *et al.* (2015). They defined strong KAP on DM at a score of 50% or higher, moderate KAP at a score of 49% to 25% and below 25% as poor KAP score. A substantial majority (95.3%) of the participants correctly indicated that blood glucose levels increase in individuals with diabetes. Furthermore, a noteworthy 90% of the respondents were aware that diabetes can have detrimental effects on various organs within the body. Additionally, 64% of the participants recognized that fasting blood glucose measurement is the most reliable method for diagnosing diabetes.

A significant number (70.7%) of the respondents believed that diabetes could be effectively managed solely through dietary control. Furthermore, an overwhelming 92.7% expressed their willingness to pursue treatment if their family members were diagnosed with diabetes. It is intriguing to note that a substantial minority (33.3%) of the participants considered alternative therapies, such as acupuncture, yoga, hypnosis, relaxation exercises, or herbal remedies, to be superior to conventional methods like diet control and medication.

In terms of practices, 55.3% participants reported engaging in daily physical activities lasting approximately 30-60 minutes, which included activities like brisk walking, household chores, and climbing stairs. Additionally, 59.3% occasionally checked their blood glucose levels while a significant proportion (30.0%) adhered to regular blood glucose monitoring. Moreover, approximately 36.7% of the participants stated their commitment to avoiding refined sugars and sugary foods due to their diabetes condition.

Table 4.5: Knowledge, attitude and practice scores on diabetes

Variables	Frequency (n=150)	Percentage (%)
Knowledge, attitude and practice scores		
Good	76	50.7
Moderate	69	46.0
Poor	5	3.3

4.7. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BMI STATUS OF PATIENTS AND THEIR LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE

As shown in Table 4.6, a chi-square analysis evaluated the introduction between knowledge score on diabetes and BMI status among diabetic patients. Significant associations were observed for some variables, while for others, the p-values did not reach the expected significance level of <0.05. Pearson chi-square correlation was performed to determine the association between the variables. Diabetes patient's knowledge was significantly associated with their nutritional status (p=0.0002). Patients who had good and moderate knowledge were more likely to be overweight/obese.

Table 4.6: BMI status of patients and their level of knowledge score

Knowledge scores	BMI status				X ²	P-value
	Underweight	Normal	Overweight	Obese		
Good	1 (0.7%)	32 (21.3%)	19 (12.7%)	24 (16.0%)	151.93	0.002
Moderate	1 (0.7%)	30 (20.0%)	16 (10.7%)	22 (14.7%)		
Poor	0 (0.0%)	3 (2.0%)	2 (1.3%)	0 (0.0%)		

4.8. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS AND THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE

Table 4.7 shows the results of the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics of patients and the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice using the chi-square test. In this

study, all of the socio-demographic indicators using Pearson chi-square correlation were significantly associated with knowledge scores of the diabetic patients. Patients' education level was significantly associated with knowledge scores ($p=0.0001$). Patients who had high level of education had a good knowledge on diabetes. Again, diabetic patients' gender ($p=0.0001$) and age ($p=0.0002$) were statistically significant with their knowledge scores. Female patients had good knowledge than male patients. Additionally, there was a significant association within marital status ($p=0.0003$) and average income ($p=0.0002$) and diabetic patients knowledge score, respectively. Furthermore, the results showed that diabetic patient's knowledge was significantly associated with relative with first degree diabetes ($p=0.0004$). Patients who had relatives with first degree diabetes were knowledgeable of diabetes.

Table 4.7: BMI status of patients and their level of knowledge score

Variables	Knowledge score			X ²	p-value
	Good	Moderate	Poor		
Gender				29.795	0.0001
Female	41 (27.3%)	39 (26.0%)	4 (2.7%)		
Male	35 (23.3%)	30 (20.0%)	1 (0.7%)		
Age groups				32.772	0.0002
31-40 years	20 (13.3%)	20 (13.3%)	3 (2.0%)		
41-50 years	34 (22.7%)	22 (14.7%)	1 (0.7%)		
51 years and above	22 (14.7%)	27 (18.0%)	1 (0.7%)		
Marital status				34.074	0.0003
Divorced	10 (6.7%)	11(7.3%)	1 (0.7%)		
Married	34 (22.7%)	32 (21.3%)	4 (2.7%)		
Single	9 (6.0%)	10 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)		
Widowed	23 (15.3%)	16 (10.7%)	0 (0.0%)		
Level of education				33.59	0.0001
Basic education	33 (22.0%)	26 (17.3%)	4 (2.7%)		
Non-formal	15 (10.0%)	14 (9.3%)	1 (0.7%)		
Secondary education	23 (15.3%)	27 (18.0%)	0 (0.0%)		
Tertiary education	5 (3.3%)	2 (1.3%)	0 (0.0%)		
Average income in Ghana cedis				62.896a	0.0002
<200	8 (5.3%)	4 (2.7%)	2 (1.3%)		
>1000	5 (3.3%)	3 (2.0%)	0 (0.0%)		
201-500	20 (13.3%)	20 (13.3%)	1 (0.7%)		
501-800	31 (20.7%)	25 (16.7%)	2 (1.3%)		
801-1000	12 (8.0%)	17 (11.3%)	0 (0.0%)		

**Relative with first degree
diabetes**

19.417a 0.004

Do not Know	14 (9.3%)	12 (8.0%)	2 (1.4%)
No	10 (6.7%)	16 (10.7%)	2 (1.3%)
Yes	52 (34.7%)	41 (27.3%)	1 (0.7%)

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

In the analysis of the sociodemographic characteristics of respondents who are adult diabetes mellitus patients, the data reveals that there is a higher prevalence of female diabetics within the study community. This finding suggests that diabetes affects both males and females, but females tend to have a higher rate of occurrence. This distribution of genders is in line with a study conducted by Amoah *et al.* (2012), which also found a predominance of females among diabetic patients. However, the incidence of diabetes can vary by gender depending on the population and location, as some studies have reported higher rates in males and others in females (Price *et al.*, 2018). This result differs from a study by Siddiqui *et al.* (2013), which suggested that diabetes is more common in males than females, although females tend to experience more complications due to inadequate disease management.

Additionally, the commonness of the disease was seen to be on the increase amidst middle-aged and older adults compared to the younger age group, in this study. This trend may be attributed to the fact that insulin resistance and impaired pancreatic islet function tend to increase with age, as reported in a similar study by Kirkman *et al.* (2012). Thus, the study data suggests that knowledge about diabetes tends to increase with advancing age among the respondents.

According to Mandpe *et al.* (2014), the nutritional status of people with diabetes is an important topic of interest as it represents a pivotal aspect in the management and control of their condition. Good nutrition is important for maintaining blood glucose levels and preventing diabetes-related complications (Mandpe *et al.*, 2014). According to the results of this study, the mean BMI of diabetic patients was 27.07 ± 5.47 . This means that most patients are obese, according to WHO recommendations. As recommended by the World Health Organization

(WHO), many diabetics can be obese. Being overweight or obese is a common propensity for type 2 diabetes (WHO, 2011).

Additionally, this study found that more than half of the diabetics were overweight or obese. The results of this study agree with the results of Aljabri *et al.* (2016), which reported that 62% of adults with type 1 diabetes in the US national sample were overweight or obese, compared with 64% of those without diabetes and 86% of adults with type 2 diabetes. Similarly, Mugharbel and Al-Mansouri (2003) concluded that the prevalence of overweight and obesity is associated with other significant complications in patients with type 2 diabetes. This study demonstrates the importance of healthcare provider training for good patient follow-up. The results of this study agree with the results of Ofori-Asenso *et al.* (2016), which found that 45.6% of adults with diabetes in Ghana were overweight or obese. When considering different regions, around 43.4% of the Ashanti region's population, 36.9% of the Central region, 32.4% of the Northern region, and 55.2% of the Greater Accra region are either overweight or obese. However, it is worth noting that these models frequently tend to overestimate the level of urbanization. According to several research publications, the prevalence of overweight and obesity has increased in Ghana between 1998 and 2016 (Ofori-Asenso *et al.*, 2016).

The study results indicated that 95.3% of the diabetic patients know that blood sugar increases when someone has diabetes. According to Kale (2023), diabetes occurs when blood glucose levels are high due to inadequate insulin production or improper body response to insulin effects. The study further showed that 30% of the diabetic patients know that diabetes is incurable with treatment and more than three-quarters (90%) of them know that diabetes can affect other organs in the body. Buse *et al.* (2009) asserted that though definition of "cure," "reversal," or "remission" of type 2 diabetes remains a contentious issue, but evidence suggests it is a reversible disease. The results of this study show that more than half of people with diabetes believe they can control their blood glucose with sugar alone. The results of this study

are consistent with the views of Alqahtani *et al.* (2020), which reported that half of the participants (n=1666, 51.9%) thought blood glucose control was good by eating wisely and not taking drugs. According to the results of this study, more than half of the patients (54.0%) used ginger, cinnamon, and fenugreek to treat their diabetes instead of taking prescription drugs, and 33.3% considered other therapies. Alternative methods such as acupuncture and yoga, hypnosis, relaxation exercises, or herbal medicine are better than diet and medication. The results of this study are in agreement with the results of Almogbel *et al.* (2022), which found ginger (47.66%), followed by vitamins and minerals (44.53%) and cinnamon (42.19%), as the most common herb used to treat diabetes. Likewise, data shows that two-thirds of people with diabetes regularly use alternative therapies, such as herbal medicines, to control blood sugar and improve their health in Africa (Ethiopia, Nigeria) (Mekuria *et al.*, 2018; Amaeze *et al.*, 2018). However, the results of this study were inconsistent with the results of two other studies conducted in Asia (Thailand) and the Middle East (Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates), which showed that up to one-third of samples lacked drugs (Alsanad *et al.*, 2018; Peltzer and Pengpid, 2019).

Regular physical activity is recommended for people with diabetes as it can have many benefits for overall health and diabetes control. Research shows that more than half (55.3%) of people with diabetes spend between 30 and 60 minutes of physical activity each day, such as brisk walking, family activities, and climbing stairs. According to Syed *et al.* (2023), exercise is the recommended first-line treatment for patients with type 2 diabetes (T2D). Moderate to vigorous exercise (150 minutes/week) is often recommended in combination with diet and/or behavior modification. When exercise is the sole treatment, it may prevent, delay, or reverse type 2 diabetes (Syeda *et al.*, 2023). Continuous body movement through skeletal muscle contraction leads to increased energy expenditure in daily life. This includes activities such as walking,

working at a desk, doing laundry, cooking, and playing sports at work and in leisure time (Hamasaki, 2016).

The study reveals a significant correlation score between diabetic patients' knowledge, attitude, and practice, and diabetes is significantly associated with relatives with type 1 diabetes ($p = 0.0004$). This finding means that patients with background history of the condition may have a higher awareness and understanding of the disease. Indeed, such families might have witnessed the effects of diabetes on loved ones and need to discuss the issue. In addition, healthcare information may be more accessible to them because of their family's experience. Having a first-degree relative with diabetes can significantly affect knowledge of diabetes, as shown in a study by Al-Maskari *et al.* (2013). Indeed, people with a family history of chronic conditions such as hypertension or diabetes may develop feelings of vulnerability, which may increase their awareness of the disease themselves (Walter *et al.*, 2004).

The results of this study showed that knowledge of diabetic patients was significantly related to nutritional status ($p=0.0002$). This means that patients with good or moderate education are at increased risk of being obese or overweight. If people with diabetes know the impact of diet and physical activity on their condition, they can make informed decisions to help them lose weight. Research exhibits key connection amidst diabetes awareness and nutritional status. People with diabetes have the propensity to opt for nutritious food because they have a better understanding of good nutrition and its impact on their condition (Doo *et al.*, 2010). Similarly, Obiri korang *et al.*, (2016), asserts that obesity rates are high among diabetics and therefore more efforts are needed to develop and implement educational programmes to accommodate changes in lifestyle (Obirikorang *et al.*, 2016).

The relationship between socio-demographic characteristics of patients and the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice scores showed that the education level of people with diabetes was significantly related to the educational score ($p = 0.0001$). Highly educated patients know

more about diabetes. These results indicate that more educated patients are more knowledgeable about diabetes and how to manage it than those with less education. This may be due to factors such as better access to information, better health literacy, and better adherence to health resources. Again, the study found that sex ($p=0.0001$) and age ($p=0.0002$) of diabetics were statistically significant for educational scores. Female patients have better knowledge than male patients. These results mean that older adults with diabetes live longer and gain more knowledge about the disease through personal experiences, interactions with healthcare providers, healthy and self-taught. For instance, Hearth et al. (2017) demonstrated a positive correlation between education and patients' increased understanding of T2D in Sri Lanka. In a similar vein, Karaoui et al. demonstrated that patient understanding of T2DM in Lebanon was favorably correlated with increased educational attainment (Karaoui). Fatema et al. (2017) found that male T2D patients in Bangladesh understood their condition better than female ones. On the other hand, Gazzaz (2020) found that women are more knowledgeable overall about diabetes, including its risk factors, symptoms, indicators, and control strategies. The results of the study indicate that having a female relative with diabetes is linked to positive attitudes and good knowledge, and that having a female relative with diabetes is linked to a good knowledge score. In addition, the results of this study show that there is a significant association between marital status ($p=0.0003$) and median income ($p=0.0002$) and knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to diabetes. This finding means that married people may benefit from a stronger support system, including a spouse, who can help them manage their diabetes. This support can help patients gain greater understanding, which in turn leads to higher learning outcomes. In addition, a higher median income is often associated with better access to health services, such as physical services, and access to specialists. Similarly, people with higher incomes may have more time to invest in education and information on how to manage their illness. This may lead to higher education scores in higher-income diabetics. The results of this

study support the argument of Le *et al.* (2021), which found that gender, marital status, education level, and monthly income were significantly related with diabetes control. Similarly, Fatema *et al.* (2017) linear regression analysis showed that educational scores were strongly associated with education level, income, place of residence, diabetes status, BMI, and attitude. However, the results of this study disagree with the results of Ghannadi *et al.* (2016), which showed that the relationship between WTP, sex, and marital status was not statistically significant.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. CONCLUSION

The participants' understanding of diabetes was generally satisfactory, with a sizable number showing knowledge of several aspects of the disease. However, more than half of the patients (54.0%) used ginger, cinnamon, and fenugreek to treat their diabetes instead of taking prescription drugs. More than half (55.3%) of the patients with diabetes spend between 30 and 60 minutes of physical activity each day, such as brisk walking, family activities, and climbing stairs.

Although the attitudes and practices of the patients varied, many of them believed that changing one's lifestyle and utilizing alternative therapies may help manage diabetes. The results underlined the significance of education and awareness programmes catered to various demographic groups, since participants' knowledge, attitudes, and practices about diabetes were affected by their educational level, gender, age, marital status, income, and family history. Additionally, the relationship between knowledge and nutritional status points to the necessity of specialized diet and weight-management programmes. Most of the patients were obese and their knowledge, attitude and practices were significantly related to nutritional status ($p=0.0002$). Additionally, the educational level of patients with diabetes was significantly related to the knowledge, attitude, and practice score ($p = 0.0001$). Again, marital status ($p=0.0003$), average income ($p=0.0002$), gender ($p=0.0001$) and age ($p=0.0002$) of patients with diabetes were statistically significant for knowledge, attitude, and practice scores. In addition, the knowledge, attitude, and practice score of diabetic patients was significantly associated with relatives with diabetes ($p = 0.004$). People with family history of diabetes, high education, high average income and are older may have a higher awareness and understanding of the disease.

6.2. RECOMMENDATION

Several suggestions can be made to enhance diabetes education, prevention, and management among the examined population in light of the study's findings and discussions:

1. **Tailored Educational Programmes:** Create instructional initiatives that are directed at particular demographic groups depending on their income, marital status, age, education, and gender. To improve each group's understanding, attitudes, and practices surrounding diabetes, these programmes should cater to their specific needs and concerns.
2. **Encourage Early Detection:** Launch campaigns aimed at raising public awareness of the value of routine diabetes tests and early detection. Stress the importance of family history in determining diabetes risk and nudge people to get screened if they have relatives who have the disease.
3. **Nutrition Advice:** Provide patients with diabetes with individualized nutrition counseling, emphasizing a healthy diet, portion control, and the management of sugary and high-calorie foods. Giving patients advice on making wise food decisions can aid in helping them maintain a healthy weight and properly control their blood sugar levels.
4. **Physical Activity Promotion:** Work with healthcare professionals to encourage diabetes patients to engage in regular physical activity. Encourage people to participate in a range of activities that fit their interests and skills, with the goal of getting at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity activity each week.
5. **Evidence-Based Therapies:** Inform patients about diabetic evidence-based therapies, such as how to take medicines, insulin, and oral agents correctly. Dispel myths regarding complementary and alternative medicine and stress the value of adhering to medical doctor's orders.

6. **Psychosocial Support:** Recognize the emotional and psychological implications of having diabetes. Provide information, counseling, and support groups to help patients deal with the difficulties of managing a chronic condition.
7. **Family Involvement:** Include family in diabetes management and education. Encourage family members to be open about their illness because their support can have a big impact on how well they stick to treatment plan.
8. **Improving Health Literacy:** Create content and tools that can be accessed by people with varying degrees of health literacy. This makes sure that all patients can properly comprehend and use knowledge about diabetes.
9. **Collaboration with Community Leaders:** Work together with local organizations and community leaders to spread knowledge about diabetes and encourage healthy lifestyle choices. Community-driven programmes can significantly increase awareness and promote constructive change.
10. **Long-Term Monitoring and Evaluation:** Set up a framework for the ongoing observation and assessment of diabetes education initiatives. To ensure continual progress, evaluate treatments' effects on participants' knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, and health outcomes on a regular basis.

It is believed that implementing the above mentioned will help healthcare organizations, policymakers, and other stakeholders improve diabetes management, prevention, and awareness within the population under study, which will ultimately lead to better health outcomes and a higher quality of life for diabetes patients.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Ethical Approval

Kwame Nkrumah
University of Science
and Technology, Kumasi

College of Health Sciences
SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AND DENTISTRY

COMMITTEE ON HUMAN RESEARCH, PUBLICATION AND ETHICS

Our Ref: CHRPE/AP/727/22

27th October 2022

Prof. F. C. Mills-Robertson
Department of Biochemistry
and Biotechnology
College of Science
KNUST-KUMASI.

Dear Sir,

LETTER OF APPROVAL

Protocol Title: "Assessing Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Diabetic Patients and its Effect on their Glycaemic Status at the Enyiresi Government Hospital."

Proposed Site: Enyiresi Government Hospital, Akyem Enyiresi.

Sponsor: Self Sponsored.

Your submission to the Committee on Human Research, Publications, and Ethics on the above-named protocol refer.

The Committee reviewed the following documents:

- A Completed CHRPE Application Form.
- Participant Information Leaflet and Consent Form.
- Research Protocol.
- Questionnaire.

The Committee has considered the ethical merit of your submission and approved the protocol. The approval is for a fixed period of one year, beginning **27th October 2022** to **26th October 2023** renewable thereafter. The Committee may, however, suspend or withdraw ethical approval at any time if your study is found to contravene the approved protocol.

Data gathered for the study should be used for the approved purposes only. Permission should be sought from the Committee if any amendment to the protocol or use, other than submitted, is made of your research data.

The Committee should be notified of the actual start date of the project and would expect a report on your study, annually or at the close of the project, whichever one comes first. It should also be informed of any publication arising from the study.

Thank you for your application.

Yours faithfully,

Rev. Prof. John Appiah-Poku.
Honorary Secretary
FOR: CHAIRMAN

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Appendix 2: Research questionnaires

Assessing Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Diabetic Patients and Its Effect on Their Glyceamic Status at the Enyiresi Government Hospital.

Consent form

The aim of this study is to assess the participants' information about diabetes. The personal information of the participants (names) will be confidential and will not be published. If you agree to participate in the study, please fill out the attached questionnaire.

- Agree**
- Disagree**

Part I - Demographic Information

Participant Name (or initials)
Age (years):
Nationality:
Occupation:
Are you working in the medical field (for example, working in a hospital - health clinic - pharmacy - medical laboratory)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes<input type="checkbox"/> No What is it:
Place of residence:
Gender: <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Male<input type="checkbox"/> Female
Marital status: <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Single<input type="checkbox"/> Married<input type="checkbox"/> Divorced<input type="checkbox"/> Widowed
Highest level of education <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Unable to read and write – no formal school education<input type="checkbox"/> Primary school<input type="checkbox"/> Middle school<input type="checkbox"/> Secondary school<input type="checkbox"/> College (Diploma)<input type="checkbox"/> University<input type="checkbox"/> Master<input type="checkbox"/> PhD

In case your higher educational level is College/ University /MSc /PhD degree, whether the specialization is related to the medical field (e.g., Faculty of Medicine, Dentistry, Pharmacy, Nursing, Laboratory Sciences)

- Yes
- No

Average monthly income in Ghana Cedis:

- <200
- 201-500
- 501- 800
- 801-1000
- >1000

First degree relatives with diabetes:

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Part II - Knowledge

Question				
Diabetes disease				
1. What happens to blood sugar in diabetes?	No change	Increase	Decrease	Don't know
2. Dysfunction of which of the following organs leads to Diabetes? If knows,		Yes	No	Don't know
• Lung				
• Kidney				
• Pancreas				
• Liver				
• Brain				
3. Is Diabetes curable with treatment?		Yes	No	Don't know
4. Which of the followings causes Diabetes?				
• Lack of insulin		Yes	No	Don't know
• Failure of the body to use insulin		Yes	No	Don't know
• Eating too much sugar		Yes	No	Don't know
• Sedentary life (or not getting enough exercise)		Yes	No	Don't know

• Stress		Yes	No	Don't know
Symptoms of Diabetes				
5. Which of the followings are usual symptoms seen in diabetic patient?				
• Increased thirst		Yes	No	Don't know
• Poor appetite / weight loss		Yes	No	Don't know
• Frequent urination		Yes	No	Don't know
• Abdominal pain		Yes	No	Don't know
• Palpitation (due to high blood sugar)		Yes	No	Don't know
• Slow healing of cuts and wounds		Yes	No	Don't know
Management of Diabetes				
6. Which of the following therapies are effective in controlling blood sugar?				
• Insulin injection		Yes	No	Don't know
• Oral medications		Yes	No	Don't know
• Regular Exercise		Yes	No	Don't know
• Avoiding sugary foods		Yes	No	Don't know
• Regular eating of (herbs, ginger and cinnamon)		Yes	No	Don't know
7. Do you think diabetes can affect other organs?				
• Stroke		Yes	No	Don't know
• Heart attack		Yes	No	Don't know
• Loss of vision		Yes	No	Don't know
• Kidney failure		Yes	No	Don't know
• Amputation		Yes	No	Don't know
8. What is the best way to diagnose Diabetes?				
• Measuring urine sugar is the best way to diagnose diabetes		Yes	No	Don't know
• Measuring blood glucose after fasting is the best way to diagnose diabetes		Yes	No	Don't know

Part-III Attitude

1. Do you think that controlling glucose with diet alone is superior to that of controlling glucose with diet and medications?	Yes	No	Don't know
2. Can long term use of metformin cause kidney damage?	Yes	No	Don't know
3. Does long term drug use cause organ failure?	Yes	No	Don't know
4. Does insulin cause harmful effects to the body?	Yes	No	Don't know
5. Do you think the use of ginger, cinnamon, and fenugreek is better for treating diabetes than prescription drugs?	Yes	No	Don't know

6. Do you think that alternative therapies (acupuncture, yoga, hypnosis, relaxation exercises or herbal remedies are better than the methods usually prescribed (diet control and medication)?	Yes	No	Don't know
7. Do you think there is no point in trying to get control of your blood sugar well, because the complications of diabetes will occur anyway"?	Yes	No	Don't know

Part IV- practice

1. Would you consider treatment if you or one of your family members are found to have diabetes?	Yes	No	Don't know
2. Do you do 30-60 minutes physical activity daily? E.g., Brisk walking, house activities, climbing staircase.	Yes	No	Don't know
3. Do you check your blood sugar regularly (at least annually)?	Yes	No	Don't know
4. Do you try to avoid refine sugar/sugary foods?	Yes	No	Don't know

Thank you!